

Comparative study of elastic wave sensing using piezoceramic and fiber optic FBG sensors

Sultan Ahamad^a, Rohan Soman^a, Paweł Malinowski^a, Tomasz Wandowski^{*,a}

^aInstitute of Fluid Flow Machinery, Polish Academy of Sciences,
Fiszera 14 St., 80–231, Gdansk, Poland

ABSTRACT

In this paper results of detailed analysis of phenomenon of elastic guided wave sensing using fibre optic strain sensors based on Bragg gratings (FBGs) and piezoelectric transducers (PZT) are presented. Attention in this research is focused on possibility of symmetric and antisymmetric guided wave mode sensing with the possibility of mode separation. For this purpose pairs of sensors located on the top and bottom surface is utilized. Moreover, mode index was introduced in order to distinguish fundamental symmetric and anti-symmetric wave modes. Authors compare sensitivity of elastic wave sensing performed by FBG sensor with one based on PZT. Piezoelectric transducers are very popular in applications related to elastic wave generation and sensing in Structural Health Monitoring and on the other hand FBG strain sensors are utilized more and more in elastic wave sensing purpose. Research was conducted for the case of aluminum panel.

Keywords: guided waves, piezoceramic transducer, fibre optic FBG sensors, aluminum panel

1. INTRODUCTION

All structures have a finite lifespan and are liable to structural defects such as corrosion, fatigue, wear, delamination. The structures not only need a significant financial investment in the manufacturing process, but these are also closely related to personal safety. For these types of issues, the Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) is gaining importance in structures, because it enhances the structure's safety and dependability while lowering maintenance costs. Among the many SHM techniques, the elastic guided waves (GW) based SHM is getting very popular nowadays. The primary issue with Lamb waves is that they are dispersive (phase and group velocities vary with frequency) and multimodal.

The GW based SHM sensing method employs a variety of sensors, but most popular are piezoelectric transducers (PZT). They can be used for wave excitation as well as sensing. The PZT sensor is inexpensive, but it requires a connection with metallic wires, which creates concerns like electromagnetic noise – electromagnetic interferences (EMI). In order to overcome EMI problem in the case of elastic wave sensing more and more popular are fiber optic strain sensors based on Bragg Grating (FBG). These sensors can be multiplexed, have small diameter and could be embedded in the structure. Due to this facts they have been considered as promising choice for GW sensing.

There large research related to application of PZT and FBG in SHM. Authors of [1] used the popular PZT transducers for wave generation while FBG sensors for elastic wave sensing. There are two approaches in measurements based on FBG sensors. In the first sensors is directly bonded to sample in order to sense the elastic waves [2]. In the second optic fibre is bonded directly to the structure but FBG is located on the part of fibre far away from bond line [3]. This approach is called remote sensing. Authors of [4] investigated deeply the sensitivity of FBG in the process of sensing of Lamb waves in aluminium plates. In the case of wave sensing authors of [5] propose passive and active sensing based for SHM purpose based on FBG. Authors of this work showed that FBG can be used in combination with a passive diffuse noise cross-correlation technique in order to extract the coherent guided waves propagating between two sensors.

*tomaszw@imp.gda.pl; phone +48 58 5225 260; <http://www.imp.gda.pl/en/o4/z1/>

This could lead to a monitoring system using only FBG sensors in the near future. Authors of [6] investigated problem of temperature influence in system based on PZT and FBG and developed calibration procedure. The PZT-FBG system was utilised for the railways tracks assessment [1]. Authors of this paper proposed diffuse ultrasonic wave (DUW) approach, referring to later arrival wave packets analysis. The authors of [7] investigated damage assessment in composite plates using guided wave based algorithms such as delay and sum. Authors proved the feasibility of active and passive imaging in composite plates using Fiber Bragg Gratings as wave sensors. More applications of FBG s for elastic wave-based SHM could be found in [8], [9].

Authors of this paper presents results of comparison of the PZT and FBG elastic wave sensing from the point of view the sensitivity and possibility of elastic wave modes separation. In this purpose pair of sensors located on the top and bottom surface were investigated and mode indicator (*MI*) was introduced. The further plans are related to use the *MI* in the damage imaging algorithm.

2. MEASUREMENT SETUP

The objects of the investigation was the panel with dimensions: 1000 mm × 1000 mm × 1 mm made out of aluminium alloy. Elastic waves generation was conducted by piezoceramic transducer (PZT) in the form of disc with diameter 10 mm and thickness 0.5 mm made out of NCE51 material. Elastic wave generation was performed using transducer located in the middle of the top surface of the panel (Figure 1). The process of elastic wave sensing was conducted in two ways. In the first, pair of FBG sensors (on the top and bottom surfaces of panel) was utilised according to the Figure 1. In the second, pair of piezoelectric transducers (the same type like actuating one) arranged in the same way like FBGs was utilised (Figure 1). The distance between sensor and wave actuation point was equal 250 mm.

Measurement by FBG is based on the edge filtering method [8], where a tunable laser is tuned to the FBG's reflectivity slope. The middle portion of the reflectivity curve is linear and has a very steep slope. As a result, a little change in the reflectivity's causes a significant difference in the optical power that the photodiode in photodetector detects (Figure 2). The amplification increases the FBG sensors' sensitivity to elastic waves.

Figure 1. Sensors arrangement on the specimen.

Figure 2. Illustration of edge-filtering measurement technique.

The whole measurement set-up was schematically presented in Figure 3. Excitation signal for wave generation was created using PXIe-5413 waveform generator and next amplified in voltage amplified in order to drive the piezoelectric actuator. In the case of PZT sensors they were connected to PXIe-5105 PXI oscilloscope card. In the case of FBG they was connected to tunable laser APEX (wavelength 1526 nm to 1567 nm) via the circulator. The third port of circulator was connected to the amplified photodetector and the signals were recorded with the oscilloscope card.

Figure 3. Scheme of experimental setup.

3. ELASTIC WAVE SENSING USING PZT AND FBG

The first step in the research was related analysis of signals gathered by the pairs of PZT and FBG sensors. Excitation signal was in the form of five cycles of sine modulated by Hann window (tone burst signal). Carrier frequency of excitation was in the range 50 kHz–250 kHz with step 10 kHz. Sensing process was conducted simultaneously by two pairs of FBG and PZT.

3.1. Signal analysis

In Figure 4 signals received by both types of sensors for excitation frequency 80 kHz were presented. In Figure 4a) signals gathered by FBG and PZT located at the top surface of the specimen are shown. Signals are similar but there are very small differences especially after second wave package. In the case of Figure 4b) signals gathered by FBG and PZT located at the bottom surface of the specimen are presented. In this case signals are similar (especially part till the second wave package) but some differences near the end of the signal could be noticed as well.

Figure 4. Signals register by FBG and PZT sensors on the: a) top surface, b) bottom surface; excitation frequency 80 kHz.

In Figure 5 similar comparison of signal but for excitation frequency 130 kHz was presented. In Figure 5a) signals gathered by FBG and PZT located at the top surface of the specimen are presented. For higher frequency of excitation there is large difference in signals for time instant 0.2 ms where is wave package registered by PZT sensor but not registered by FBG. Later in the time (instant 0.3 ms) there is wave package registered by FBG but not sensed by PZT.

Moreover, there are still differences near the end of the signal. Similar situation is observed for signals gathered by FBG and PZT located at the bottom surface of the specimen – see Figure 5b). There are wave packages registered by FBG and not by PZT and contrary situation.

Figure 5. Signals register by FBG and PZT sensors on the: a) top surface, b) bottom surface; excitation frequency 130 kHz.

Next step was related to signal analysis in the frequency domain. In this purpose, spectrograms presenting the data in the time-frequency manner were utilised. In this purpose short time Fourier transform is utilised (STFT). Spectrogram illustrates the distribution of signal energy both in the time and frequency. In Figure 6 spectrograms created for signals gathered by FBG and PZT located on the top surface of specimen are presented. In both cases wave excitation frequency was equal 130 kHz. This frequency was chosen in order to present interesting observation. In Figure 6a) spectrogram for the signal gathered by FBG sensor was presented. The wave energy is concentrated in narrow band for the centre frequency 130 kHz, what is connected with the nature of excitation tone burst signal. Wave energy is concentrated along the time axis in the instances where the elastic wave packages are registered in time domain signals (see Figure 5a). In the Figure 6b) spectrogram for the signal gathered by PZT sensor was presented. In this case wave energy is also concentrated in narrow band with centre frequency 130 kHz. However, elastic wave energy is also concentrated in narrow band with centre frequency ~260 kHz. The level of energy is significantly smaller in this second band than in the one related to excitation. In the case of FBG this effect was not so intensive. Due to this phenomenon received signals were filtered using narrow band filter (post-processing in software).

Figure 6. Spectrograms of signals registered by: a) FBG, b) PZT; excitation frequency 130 kHz.

Analysing both spectrograms it could be noticed that not all wave packages (represented as energy concentration regions along time axis) for PZT and FBG correspond to each other.

3.2. Elastic wave modes identification

Next step was related to elastic wave mode identification. Due to utilised excitation frequency up to 250 kHz in the aluminium specimen with the thickness 1 mm, only fundamental symmetric (S_0) and anti-symmetric (A_0) modes propagate. This could be determined solving the Rayleigh-Lamb frequency equations which allow to plot dispersion curves.

In Figure 7 interesting method of presentation of time signals gathered by sensors for different excitation frequencies was presented. In the Figure 7a) example of signals received by the FBG sensor located on the bottom side of the panel was presented. Excitation frequencies were in the range 50kHz–250 kHz. Signals are grouped according the excitation frequency and the absolute values of signals were plotted. Such presentation form allows to distinguish the wave packages and what is important, allows to observe the changes of wave propagation velocity in the function of frequency (dispersion). In Figure 7b) example of presentation of signals for the FBG sensor located on the top side of the panel is showed. Results in the both cases of FBG (bottom and top) are very similar.

Figure 7. Gathered signals presented in time-frequency manner for FBG on the: a) bottom surface, b) top surface.

It could be noticed that first wave package (time ~ 0.1 ms) only slightly changes the velocity of propagation. However, second wave package (0.15 ms for 250 kHz and 0.25 for 50 kHz) changes significantly the velocity of propagation in the function of frequency. It could be concluded that the first wave package is related to S_0 mode while second one to A_0 (more dispersive). This could be determined based on the fact that these are first two wave packages that directly propagated from actuator to the sensor. Next indicator are the phenomenon of the velocity change in function of frequency. It need to be underlined that wave package with small energy between mentioned wave packages could be related to wave reflections between PZT transducers (~ 0.12 ms). Wave packages received later are related to wave reflections from panel edge.

In Figure 8a) example of signals received by the PZT sensor located on the bottom side of the panel and in the Figure 8b) by the PZT located on the bottom side are presented in the same manner like in the case of FBG sensors. The same situation could be observed in the case of two first wave packages. First is related to wave mode with almost constant velocity of propagation (S_0) and second for velocity changing with frequency (A_0). The wave packages between S_0 and A_0 are for the case of PZT almost not visible.

Moreover comparing results for FBG (Figure 7) and PZT (Figure 8) it could be noticed that sensitive to wave packages received after A_0 is different for both types of sensors. There is wave package (time 0.2 ms for 250 kHz) for the case of PZT (Figure 8) not registered by FBG (Figure 7). On the other hand, there is wave package (time 0.3 ms for 250 kHz) for the case of FBG (Figure 7) not registered by PZT (Figure 8). Due to the fact that in case of first mode (observed in PZT signals) the velocity of the mode (below 100 kHz) is almost constant it looks like this is S_0 wave mode. Moreover, it could be noticed that energy of S_0 wave package below frequency 100 kHz is significantly reduced while in the A_0 mode there is no such effect. The second one observed in FBG signals probably is also related to S_0 . However, further research is need in order to determine mode type in time instant 0.3 ms for 250 kHz in Figure 7.

Moreover, there is lack of differences in modes in the case of PZT (Figure 7) and FBG (Figure 8) signals for frequency below 100 kHz. The same situation was observed in the case of signals for frequency 80 kHz in Figure 4. While as the differences are large for higher frequencies like for example 130 kHz (Figure 5).

Figure 8. Gathered signals presented in time-frequency manner for PZT on the: a) bottom surface, b) top surface.

Next step was related to determination of velocities of identified S_0 and A_0 modes (based on first arrival – direct path). In the Figure 9 velocities of S_0 and A_0 mode for PZT and FBG transducers located on both surfaces of specimen was plotted in function of frequency.

Figure 9. Dispersion curves based on FBG and PZT measurements and numerical data.

In this purpose distance between actuator and sensor (250 mm) was utilised and time of wave package registration (time of flight, ToF). Moreover, in Figure 9 theoretical values of S_0 and A_0 propagation velocities were marked as solid lines. These velocities were determined based on solution of Rayleigh Lamb equation for the considered aluminium specimen. It could be noticed that experimentally determined velocities agree with theoretical ones.

Further step was related to extraction of amplitudes of S_0 and A_0 modes in the function of frequency. This was done for the both types of sensors. In the Figure 10a) results for the case of FBG sensors were plotted.

Figure 10. Amplitudes of S_0 and A_0 modes in function of frequency for a) FBG sensors, b) PZT sensors.

It could be noticed that below 130 kHz amplitudes of A_0 mode are larger than S_0 one. For the frequencies above 13 kHz S_0 mode has larger amplitude than A_0 mode. In Figure 10b) results for the case of PZT sensors were presented. Here similar situation is observed. The S_0 mode have smaller amplitude than A_0 for frequencies below 130 kHz while situation is inverse for frequencies above 130 kHz. Moreover, in the case of lowest frequencies the ratio of S_0/A_0 is smaller for PZT than for FBG. For largest frequencies S_0/A_0 ratio is larger for PZT than for FBG.

Using the amplitude differences of A_0 and S_0 it is possible to generate the one type of mode with dominating amplitude over the second one if the frequency differs from 130 kHz.

4. SYMMETRIC AND ANTI-SYMMETRIC MODE SEPARATION

Symmetric and anti-symmetric modes could be distinguished using the pair of sensors on both sides of specimen. In the Figure 11a) comparison of signals gathered by FBG on the top and bottom surface of panel was presented. In this case excitation frequency was equal 100 kHz. It could be noticed that in the case of first wave package both signals have the same phase while in the case of second wave package they are out of phase. This is due to the symmetrical (in respect to the thickness) deformation of material during the propagation of S_0 wave mode (first wave package). Material deformations during the propagation of A_0 mode are anti-symmetrical what results in the difference of phase in the case of second wave package (A_0). Authors decide to use this features to create the mode indicator (MI) based on phase of pair of signals. In order to validate the MI performance the registered signals (raw) were additionally noised (random noise with amplitude up to 25% of maximum signal amplitude).

Figure 11. Comparison of signals registered by FBG sensors on the top and bottom surface: a) raw signal, b) with additional noise and time shift; excitation frequency 100 kHz.

This noise could be induced by operating condition in the real situation. Moreover, time shift of the one signal was created in order to simulate the situation of not perfectly alignment of two sensors. Example of such noised signals which one was additionally shifted are presented in Figure 11b).

Mode indicator at time instant i could be formulated as signals multiplication:

$$MI 1(i) = S_T(i)S_B(i) \quad (1)$$

where: S_T – time signal received by the sensor on the top side, S_B – time signal received by sensor on the bottom side. Results of obtained using $MI 1$ parameter in the case of signals presented in Figure 11a) are presented in Figure 12. In the case of symmetric mode $MI 1$ has positive values where negative values in the case of antisymmetric mode. In order to amplify the indication of this parameter following modification was performed using the envelope of one signal created by Hilbert transform:

$$MI 2(i) = \frac{S_T(i)S_B(i)}{|Hilbert(S_T(i))|} \quad (2)$$

The results in the form of $MI 2$ parameter are plotted also in Figure 12. Values of this parameter were amplified in comparison to $MI 1$ but in the case of anti-symmetric mode there is little jump from negative to positive values. This will not allow to distinguish modes considering the negative/positive value of $MI 2$.

Figure 12. Comparison of $MI 1$ and $MI 2$ parameters for raw signals.

In order to solve this problem $MI 2$ was filtered with filter based on moving averages. Filtered indicator was named $MI 3$ and its values were plotted together with $MI 2$ in Figure 13. It could be noticed that the $MI 3$ works properly. It is possible to distinguish mode type based on positive/negative value of $MI 3$. First wave package (S_0) is related to positive values of $MI 3$ while second (A_0) with negative. This could be easily noticed in Figure 14a) where the $MI 3$ plot is compared with signals gathered by two FBG sensors.

Figure 13. Comparison of $MI 2$ and $MI 3$ parameters for for signals: a) raw, b) with additional noise and time shift.

In order to validate the performance of $MI 3$ in situation that could be meet in the real conditions the same analysis was performed in the case of signals with additional noise and time shift. Comparison of $MI 2$ and $MI 3$ for such situation was presented in Figure 13b).

In this case time shift of one signal (see Figure 11b) caused problem of proper work of both indicators what could be noticed in Figure 13b). In the case of both modes there are positive and negative values what does not allow to distinguish modes. This could be better noticed in Figure 14b). In order to solve this problem signal compensation based on time shifting in order to achieve the maximum correlation of signals is conducted.

Results of signals compensation is presented in Figure 15 where both signals with noise are perfectly aligned. In the Figure 16 comparison of $MI 3$ values for the cases of: raw data (referential–without noise), signals with additional noise and shifted in time and compensated ones (with additional noise) are presented. In the case of signal with time shift the $MI 3$ does not work properly. In the case of referential signals and noised signals indicator works properly.

Figure 14. Comparison of signals with $MI\ 3$ parameter for: a) raw signals, b) signals with noise and time shift.

Figure 15. Comparison of signals registered by FBG sensors on the top and bottom surface after compensation.

Figure 16. Comparison of $MI\ 3$ parameter for case of raw, noised and compensated signals.

These results showed that it is possible to use proposed mode indicator in the case of simple aluminium panel. This indicator need to be validated further in the case of damage in the panel together with damage imaging algorithm.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper authors investigated the sensitivity of PZT and FBG sensors for the case of A_0 and S_0 wave modes. First arrival of fundamental modes S_0 and A_0 was registered through the both types of sensors with similar result. There were differences related to further arrival of S_0 and A_0 modes visible especially above the frequency 100 kHz. Bellow this frequency S_0 wave mode energy is very small in comparison to A_0 . The A_0 wave mode has larger amplitude than S_0 mode for frequencies bellow 130 kHz while as situation is opposite for frequencies above 130 kHz. This is observed for both types of sensors. Ratio of A_0 to S_0 amplitudes for low frequency is lower for PZT than FBG while situation is opposite for highest frequencies.

Phase of signals gathered by pair of sensors (on the top and bottom side of panel) and its multiplication could be utilised for the purpose of distinguish symmetric and anti-symmetric fundamental mode. Mode indicating index was introduced and was validated in the case of noised and time shifted signals (simulating not perfectly alignment of sensors). Proposed indicator works correctly for noised signals but for time shifted signals compensation based on signals correlation need to be utilised for its proper works.

Further research will be related to further validation of proposed mode indicator in the case of case of damage and more complex structure. Moreover, research related to implementation of this indicator in damage imaging algorithm will be conducted.

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